

We have tended to build a society in which learning through primal intimacies has been removed from the formal streams. The making of a desirable India of the 21st century would need such an amalgam, a seamless connection between the rich and diverse subterranean systems of learning still current in our society and the formal systems we have instituted and recognize. I believe it can happen. It will involve all that Kalam and Rajan have dreamt, and a lot more. After all we are talking of India.

This book by Kalam with Rajan is no ordinary book. It will excite, provoke and even annoy a lot of people. That is why it should be in all libraries and on the desk of everyone who dreams about the future of India. Even the controversy it generates would be valuable.

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The International Visibility of Danish and Scandinavian Research 1988-1996. Peter Ingwersen. Centre for Information Studies, Royal School of Library and Information Science, Copenhagen, Denmark. [CIS Report No. 5], 1998. p. 72.

Davidson Frame had suggested a few years ago that if one wanted to measure the volume of significant research performed by different countries, one could count the number of papers indexed in *Science Citation Index* (SCI), but if one wanted to make a more comprehensive survey then one could use comprehensive subject databases. In the early eighties, Udai N. Singh of Birla Institute of Technology, Ranchi, collected publication data from *INSPEC-Physics Abstracts* and citation data from the print version of *SCI* to map the impact of hitech physics research – holography, lasers, liquid crystals and superconductivity – in India, Israel, Canada and Australia. Singh collected the entire data manually! Peter Ingwersen has carried out an online publication analysis for Scandinavian countries, combining comprehensive abstracting services – *BIOSIS*, *Medline*, *Chemical*

Abstracts, *Psychinfo*, *INSPEC*, and *Compendex* – and the three multidisciplinary citation indexes – *SCI*, *SSCI*, and *A* and *HCI*. Like Paul Bourke and Linda Butler have done for Australia and Steven Katz and Diana Hicks have done for the UK, Ingwersen has provided quantitative publication indicators for Denmark and Scandinavia. While the Australian and the British colleagues devoted much time to standardize data elements, Ingwersen provides two types of publication indicators, viz. the 'Gross International Visibility' (GIV) and the 'Central International Visibility' (CIV) for all of science in Denmark as well as for nine central scientific domains. For Finland, Norway and Sweden he has provided only CIV. The GIV is the annual publication activity relative to the world (or regional) activity monitored by means of the core international bibliographic databases (such as *BIOSIS* for Biology) and citation databases. CIV is limited to publications indexed in ISI's citation databases. Ingwersen has tried hard to isolate entries that may be found both in one of the citation indexes and in the domain-dependent databases, to avoid duplicate counting. He has also compared his data with TemaNord report on science in the OECD countries, published in 1994.

Besides giving data on Scandinavia's share of the world's publications, Ingwersen provides an idea of publication productivity (in relation to expenditure on R and D). Scandinavia is strong in the life sciences, and particularly in biomedicine, with a 30% higher average publication activity, but weak in chemistry. For those who would like to have a quick glance, Ingwersen's two-page summary (Chapter 12) can give a clear idea of the major results. The large number of tables, figures, and bar charts also help. The subjects and subfields constituting the nine central domains (biology, biomedicine, clinical medicine, social medicine, chemistry, geoscience, physics and mathematics, technology, social sciences and humanities) are given in an appendix.

There are some methodological problems. Ingwersen has used *Medline* as the core subject dependent database for both biomedicine and clinical medicine. But the numbers of *Medline* entries from Denmark differ: 23,954 in the

section on biomedicine (page 26) and 12,969 in the section on clinical medicine (page 30). Besides, not all *Medline* entries can be credited to either biomedicine or clinical medicine. Physics and mathematics are clubbed and *Inspec* is used as the core subject database. The author could have tried *Mathsci* or *Compumath Citation Index* as a core bibliographic database for Mathematics.

The book does not explain the data collection and analysis methods in detail, perhaps because the author has described them in the two journal articles given in the references section on page 62. The writing style in general could have been improved with the help of an editor.

I look forward to the author's forthcoming report on international citation impacts of Scandinavian science.

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The Book of Indian Trees. K. C. Sahni. Bombay Natural History Society. Oxford University Press, YMCA Library Building, Jaisingh Road, New Delhi 110 001. 1998. 230 pp. Price: Rs 275.

Trees are the largest, tallest and the longest living organisms that form a continuum from soil to air. Ignoring the wisdom of the tribals and the rural poor, who enjoy the blessings of trees and use them sparingly to meet their necessities, the urban societies have clear-felled trees in forests for economic assets, causing severe environmental damage and rapid extinction of biota. *The Book of Indian Trees* has come at an appropriate time when the immense value of trees is being realized as important renewable resources not merely for economic well-being but also for ecological security, tranquility and aesthetic living.

The author K. C. Sahni is a distinguished botanist, who has done research and has taught generations of Indian Forest Service probationers at FRI, Dehra Dun. He has botanized extensively in Eastern Himalaya, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Sri Lanka and Sudan and

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has a first hand knowledge of trees. Sahni has expended his unbound energy and expertise to bring out a delightful and beautifully illustrated book that would be helpful in recognizing the most common native and naturalized trees in the field, learn about their characteristics and interactions with animals. To shortlist 153 trees of the Indian sub-continent (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan, Myanmar and Sri Lanka) is a herculean task. His selection includes dicotyledons, monocotyledons, gymnosperms and tree ferns. The author has achieved a blend of scientific accuracy, lucid style and an absorbing interest.

The narration on each tree gives the common English name (some have been coined by the author), the full botanical (Latin) name, its family, names in a few Indian languages, Burmese and occasionally Nepalese. Understandably the major part of the book (pp. 16–120) is devoted to individual species. Field identification marks, general description, features of the bark, leaves, flowers, fruits, seeds, distribution and recurring seasonal events like leaf fall, flowering and fruiting are valuable tips to the users. Like humans, trees have their own personality. Sahni leads you to discover the uniqueness of each tree. The items entered under 'Miscellaneous' pertain to uses, legends, folklore and ecological notes.

The technical names of plants consist of two epithets, often so bizarre as to dissuade neophytes from studying plants. Yet these names are accepted by scientists the world over. For those who wish to take up natural history as a serious hobby, Sahni's notes on etymology of botanical names are spicy. For example, the name *Tamarindus indica* L. (the tamarind) is derived from the Arabic 'Tamar hindi', meaning the date of Hindoostan. Most people may not know that the tamarind tree was brought by the Arabs to India from Africa. The genus *Dillenia* was named by Linnaeus to commemorate Johann Jacob Dillenius (1648–1747), a German botanist and Professor of Botany at Oxford. Linnaeus stated '*Dillenia* has of all plants the showiest flower, *Dillenius* is likewise conspicuous among botanists'. Sahni has traced the interesting origins of even common names! The fruits of *Dillenia indica* are dispersed by wild ele-

phants, hence the name elephant apple. 'Chi Naar' (*Platanus orientalis*) is a Persian word meaning 'what a fire', because the leaves turn golden yellow to flaming red in late autumn. Chinar trees were introduced to Kashmir 400 years ago by the Mughals. A tree with a circumference of 16 m was recorded at Bijbihara near Srinagar. The reviewer had the good fortune to see this living cathedral and keep a photographic record. *Excoecaria agallocha* is called blinding tree! The irritating milky juice can cause blindness when it drops into the eyes. *Diospyros marmorata* is named zebrawood on account of the prominent jet-black stripes in the finished wood.

The reviewer wishes to share some curious pieces of information provided by Sahni. He reports that the wood of only female trees of the English willow (*Salix alba* ssp. *coerulea*) introduced to Kashmir are used for manufacturing cricket bats and the male trees are rejected! Jungly Dungi (*Tetrameles nudiflora*) is a favourite tree for animals. Bees build their hives on the canopy and hornbills their nests. Wood-peckers hollow out the soft wood and nest in the holes arranged in a vertical line on the trunk. *Amherstia nobilis* is often claimed as the most beautiful tree in the world; and I entirely agree. At the entrance to the Peradeniya Botanical Garden in Sri Lanka, you can behold a magnificent grove of these spectacular trees. A particular mango tree in Chandigarh has a trunk of 9.6 m girth, a crown spread of 2250 sq.m, with an annual yield of 17 m tonnes of fruit! Tigers clean their claws on the bark of *Bischofia javanica*, in the sub-Himalayan tracts, causing the red, blood-like juice to ooze out. The author aptly suggests the name 'tiger tree' for it. The lion-tailed macaque of Kerala and Tamil Nadu spends most of its time on the canopy of *Karayani tree* (*Cullenia exarillata*) consuming its fruits.

The author has given highlights of a few representative trees, especially those not covered in the text, that occur in 11 different regions of the Indian sub-continent from Western Himalaya to Eastern Himalaya, the north-west region to the Gangetic plain, West coast, Central India, Deccan and Karnataka, Assam and Meghalaya, Andaman

and Nicobar Islands, Sri Lanka and Myanmar. Sahni recommends the reader to consult a few major books on trees listed in the bibliography.

Agnes Arber, the celebrated English botanist believed that line drawings are creations of the mind and the eye. P. Sharma has proved this dictum by the neat, life-like sketches of 70 trees. Some figures stand out for their excellence and fidelity that would aid in field identification. The reviewer is aware of the frustrating hardships in photographing entire trees in their original habitat. Dev Raj Agarwal and M. R. Almeida are to be complimented for the magnificent colour plates. The cover photograph of the flame of the forest by the noted naturalist E. P. Gee is superb. The silhouettes of 11 trees portray their characteristic canopy architecture.

The Oxford University Press was known for producing nearly error-free books in the past. Lately this reputation has not been maintained. There are several typographical and technical errors which need rectification in the next edition. 'Peridenya' (p. 213) should read 'Peradeniya'; under Oleaceae, (p. 213) stamens 7 should read stamens 2 or 4. In Bombacaceae stamens are not monadelphous but occur in 5–15 bundles attached to petals; 'National Botanic Gardens, Calcutta' should read 'Indian Botanic Gardens'. On p. 57 it is reported that the mere presence of neem leaves is believed to keep an area free from malaria. This is an overstatement. This pulp from the pods of tamarind is mentioned as used to season curries, chutneys and ice-creams. It is mainly used as souring agent in curries and chutneys, as a source of home remedies and for extracting tartaric acid. On p. 88 it is stated that 'The flowers of *Butea monosperma* are fertilized by babblers, sunbirds and other birds'. This is to be verified. A large number of birds and insects visit the flowers and rob the nectar by making a hole in the calyx cup. Parakeets destroy the floral parts to lap up the nectar. The work done by Rajesh Tandon at Delhi University has shown that only sunbirds are true pollinators.

Some of the definitions given to terms in the glossary need rectification and simplification.

The above minor points do not reduce the merit of the painstaking, dedicated

and valuable book written by Sahni for the interested lay person. A book becomes a treasure when an amateur finds it exciting, friendly and instructive and even the expert finds new information and insights. *The Book of Indian Trees* belongs to this category and should be a prized possession and a companion to students of natural history, forestry, botany and wild-life. The Bombay Natural History Society deserves our gratitude in supporting this publication. We should thank the Department of Science and Technology (DST), New Delhi, and Purshotamdas Thakurdas and Divaliba Charitable trust, Mumbai for providing financial support to keep the cost reasonable for those who wish to buy a personal copy. A paper back edition would be more welcome to students.

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Mountains of the World: A Global Priority. Bruno Messerli and Jack D. Ives (eds). Parthenon Publishing Group, One Blue Hill Plaza, Pearl River, New York 10965, USA. 1997. 495 pp.

Embodying a collection of 22 papers by preponderantly western scholars, bound together with a sense of commitment for a mountain development agenda, this wonderfully informative, aptly illustrated and eruditely crafted work presents individual perceptions and findings, and incisive analyses of conditions and problems of highlands and highlanders. The canvas of the treatise is vast – (i) the ethnic diversity, culture, spiritual heritage, comparative inequalities, poverty and plight, and

conflicts and dilemmas of mountain peoples; (ii) the vulnerable positions of the women and children in highly stressful situations obtaining in the mountains; (iii) the subsistence agriculture tied inexorably to animal husbandry and the critical fragmentation of landholdings and resultant acute deficiency despite high labour inputs which forces the young and the competent out of the mountains; (iv) the glaring fact of inequalities between highland and lowland areas in the matter of developments, culminating in the relegation of mountain states to the periphery of development programmes, putting them in the 'shadows of economic centres' located in the plains and subjecting highlands to short-term exploitation of resources; (v) the impact on environment and mountain communities of tourism ('socially, culturally and economically a double-edge sword') and amenity migration (without compensatory participation of emigrants in development and community affairs) (vi) the mountain physiography, ecosystems, biodiversity, ecological interaction and forestry; (vii) the natural assets, assessment and conservation of water and mineral resources, hydrological regimes, floral cover and watershed management; (viii) the problems and perils of development activities; (ix) the mountain hazards and the alternative sources of energy and risk-coping measures, (x) and agenda and strategy for sustainable development.

As the editors themselves admit 'the book is a balance between documentary and theoretical materials'. It brings out eloquently the perceptions, the philosophy and the life-long mission of the two editors – Bruno Messerli and Jack Ives. Written as the articles are by more than two dozen authors from different countries, there is understandably no 'consistent and unanimous message'. The editors anticipate that in the 21st century the humankind will increasingly depend on mountain resources and em-

phasize the need for initiating practical steps for sustainable development.

Exuding enormous sympathy for the marginalized communities of the mountains, the book about the mountains, ironically, does not provide opportunity to even one active scholar/worker from the world's highest mountain Himalaya to write about his land, his people, his experiences and perceptions and his blueprint of development dreams (Alas, the thinking/working man of the Himalaya mountain stands out in the margin!).

The quintessence of the development agenda is spelled out in Chapter 15 – 'Sustainable mountain development occurs when the needs and aspirations of mountain people and the capacity of the natural resource-base to supply them are in balance over time'.

There is an erudite piece (Chapter 17) on the controlling factors and trends of climate changes in the mountains and their impacts on the flora, fauna and human endeavours.

The last chapter provides the synthesis of the book and spells out prerequisites for perspective development, coping with hazards, and policy and strategy for sustainable development. There is a strong plea for having political will for undoing inequalities, for having appreciation and support for indigenous knowledge and management systems, and for open and continual dialogue between the stake-holders.

If you are involved in the development of mountains, or have love for mountains and highlanders, then you must read this book and have it in your shelves.

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